

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STRUCTURE OF MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS OF PORPHINE

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Abstract

The bonds of the cyclic system of porphine molecules have an effect on the properties and characteristics of these molecules. Complexes obtained from porphines have an effect on the spectral properties of the components. The highest spectral changes are observed in Fe-porphines, since they form particularly strong complexes when interacting with CO, pyridine and water. The singly charged ions of porphines are represented by short-lived intermediate compounds. They can quickly transition to doubly charged ions, since their structures are unstable and one of the central N atoms is not equivalent to the remaining atoms.

Keywords: porphine, communication, complex, spectrum, chlorophyll

It is enough to list some compounds of the porphyrin series to make it clear how important a comprehensive study of these compounds is. These compounds include: chlorophyll - the green pigment of the photosynthetic apparatus of plants; heme - a red pigment that provides the transport of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the bloodstream; prosthetic groups of cytochromes - biocatalysts that regulate tissue respiration; phthalocyanines - widely used synthetic compounds, such as dyes.

Porphyrin and its derivatives form complexes with various metals, replacing the H atom in the center of the molecule. Divalent metal complex of porphyrin (M-porphyrin) [2]:

M - porfin

The bonds of the cyclic system of porphine molecules have an impact on the properties and characteristics of these molecules. Measurements of the limiting polarization of the luminescence of symmetrically substituted derivatives of the molecules lead to the conclusion that the compounds of these molecules can be included in the point symmetry group D_{4h} . This means that the bonding bonds of the system, as a result of the delocalization of the π -electrons, all four pyrrole rings, four M – N bonds and other symmetrically located atoms and molecules, are equivalent [4].

Porphines and their analogues form associations or complexes when interacting with each other or with molecules of the environment. Porphine complexes influence the spectral properties of the components. The highest spectral changes can be observed in Fe-porphines, since particularly strong complexes are formed when interacting with CO, pyridine and water. The chlorophyll molecule provides readiness for elementary photochemical reactions when interacting with molecules of the environment. Porphines are known to be amphoteric compounds. All four nitrogen atoms of the porphine molecule can serve as proton acceptors as basic centers. NH groups are capable of losing protons under certain conditions, i.e. act as acid centers. The

formation of relatively stable photoreduced chlorophyll forms is observed in pyridine. According to some considerations, this stability is associated with an "intermediate" state between the pigment molecule of the proton and the basic molecule of the environment, which accepts its electron.

The formation of these relatively stable compounds is only possible if the proton's bond with the pigment molecule is optimal to a certain extent.

If we denote the neutral molecule of porphine as H_2P , then in principle 6 of its ionic forms are possible: $(H/D)^-$ and $D/2$ when interacting with strong bases, and $(H_3P)^+$, $(H_4P)^{2+}$, $(H_5P)^{3+}$ and $(H_6P)^{4+}$ with acids. The dianion and dication forms of porphines can be distinguished as $Na^{2+}P^{2-}$ and $(H_4P)^{2+}Cl^{2-}$ salts. When storing tetraphenylporphine and tetraphenylchlor pigments in gaseous HCl, their dehydrochloric compounds are formed.

From the measurements of luminescence polarization it is concluded that the porphyrin dication $(H_4P)^{2+}$ has the D_{4h} point group symmetry, like the metalloporphine molecule. Therefore, in the dication, the excess charges are distributed evenly over the connecting bonds of the cyclic system and are equivalent to four pyrrole nuclei. The position and width of the absorption bands in the IR spectra in the region of the valence vibrations of the NH bonds of tetraphenylporphyrin dehydrochloride and tetraphenylchlorine indicate that these bonds have an ionic $(NH)^+$ character [4]. Therefore, in the structures of porphyrin and chlorine dications, the excess charges are mainly concentrated near the NH bonds and are distributed evenly between them. The formulas of the dication and dianion:

porfin dikationu porfin dianionu

The singly charged ions of porphyrins are observed in exceptional cases. It is believed that in the presence of some aqueous detergents, the absorption spectra of the protoporphyrin monocation are observed [1]. Singly charged porphine ions exist only as short-lived intermediates due to their structural instability. They can quickly transition to doubly charged ions, since their structures are unstable and one of the central N atoms is not equivalent to the remaining atoms. When chlorine interacts with acids, the equivalence of the pyrrole rings is broken by hydrogenation of one of their side double bonds, and the spectra of both the dication and the dianion can be observed [3].

This section discusses the photoreduction reactions of porphyrin pigments and the effects of these reactions on molecular structures. These reactions occur by adding hydrogen atoms to pigment molecules, which leads to significant changes in molecular structures. It examines how different porphyrin and chlorine derivatives form different molecular structures as a result of photoreduction and the effects of this reaction on molecular symmetry and electronic structures. Photoreduction is an important chemical reaction that changes the chemical structures of pigment molecules and affects their electronic properties. In the photoreduction

reaction, H atoms are added to pigment molecules, which leads to the formation of new bonds in the molecules. Pigments such as chlorophyll, pheophytin and bacterial chlorophyll undergo photoreduction and it is important to understand the effects of this process on molecular structure. It is noted that the complexity of this process and the response of pigments to photoreduction depend on various conditions.

References

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